

FIC Fighters

FIC-Fighters Deliverable D5.2

Stakeholder Mapping

Summary: This deliverable provides a comprehensive stakeholder mapping within the scope of the FIC-Fighters project, focusing on the identification and categorisation of key actors involved in or affected by phosphogypsum (PG) deposits, management and valorisation. The objective of this mapping exercise is to establish a structured approach to stakeholder engagement, ensuring that diverse perspectives are integrated into decision-making processes and governance frameworks.

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive stakeholder mapping within the scope of the FIC-Fighters project, focusing on the identification and categorisation of key actors *involved in or affected by* phosphogypsum (PG) deposits, management and valorisation. The objective of this mapping exercise is to establish a structured approach to stakeholder engagement, ensuring that diverse perspectives are integrated into decision-making processes and governance frameworks.

The stakeholder mapping process follows a systematic methodology that classifies stakeholders based on their power, interests and role in PG-related activities. This includes actors from industry and business, policy agents and public administration, academia and research organisations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), civil society, and media representatives.

This deliverable identifies two key social engagement and governance approaches in the FIC-Fighters project:

1. Bridging the gap between scientific knowledge and social perception regarding PG stacks, enabling the development of effective communication strategies and tools that enhance public awareness and stakeholder understanding.
2. Facilitating early and transparent engagement with local communities and key stakeholders, ensuring that project activities are aligned with societal needs, regulatory requirements, and sustainability objectives.

The insights gained from this stakeholder mapping will inform subsequent project activities, including social impact assessment (D5.3), participatory processes (D5.4), and policy recommendations. Future engagement and communication actions will be designed to be inclusive, accessible, and tailored to the interests of different stakeholder groups, ensuring their active participation and contribution to the project's goals.

By providing a structured and evolving framework for stakeholder engagement, this deliverable strengthens the FIC-Fighters project's commitment to socially and environmentally responsible PG management, ensuring that the different solutions are designed in collaboration with all relevant actors.

The resulting stakeholder database is a dynamic tool that will be updated along the project lifecycle as new actors emerge throughout the different phases of the project development.

1. Preliminary concepts

This deliverable D5.2 "PG Stakeholder Mapping" represents a foundational phase in WP5 (ESG perspectives), which focuses on the identification and categorisation of key actors involved in or affected by phosphogypsum (PG) management.

The FIC-Fighters project is committed to ensuring continuous and structured engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders, integrating their perspectives into governance frameworks and decision-making processes throughout the project's lifespan. Specifically, this exercise has been carried out with particular care at the community level in the different case studies considered, due to the project's focus on strengthening local democracies. However, it has to be considered that the social acceptance of PG-related activities operates at multiple levels, from local communities (concerned with environmental,

health and economic impacts) to broader societal perceptions, where media and public discourse play a critical role. The FIC-Fighters project acknowledges these interconnected scales of influence and adopts a comprehensive stakeholder mapping approach to capture and analyse these dynamics effectively.

Through a preliminary and systematic analysis of stakeholders, this deliverable sets the groundwork for targeted engagement and communication strategies that are tailored to the specific interests and levels of power of different stakeholder groups.

Given the increasing saturation of information in modern society, future participatory actions will be designed to be engaging, inclusive and adaptable to the needs of each target group. These efforts will ensure that stakeholder involvement is meaningful, well-received, and impactful, reinforcing the project's commitment to socially and environmentally responsible PG management.

1.1. Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder engagement ensures inclusive dialogues and collaboration with all relevant parties and it is essential for:

- **Understanding societal concerns.** The project can identify and respond to community expectations, regulatory requirements, and other challenges, fostering a constructive relationship with different actors.
- **Encouraging collaboration and knowledge exchange.** Stakeholders contribute diverse perspectives, scientific expertise, and local insights, improving the project's ability to develop sustainable and effective governance strategies.
- **Enhancing decision-making and planning.** Stakeholder engagement helps the project anticipate challenges, improve regulatory compliance, and facilitate transparent policymaking.

Stakeholder mapping involves the identification, categorisation, and graphical representation of all relevant stakeholders who may be affected by or have an interest in the project's activities. This process ensures that engagement efforts are structured, transparent and responsive, facilitating effective participation from all relevant actors.

1.2. Stakeholder categories

The approach applied categorises stakeholders into the following key groups:

- **Industry and business.** Companies directly or indirectly involved in phosphoric acid production, phosphogypsum (PG) stack management, processing, and remediation, as well as businesses that use the end products of the process (such as detergent companies, paper, fertiliser or cement companies) and other business that may benefit from project outcomes.
- **Clusters & Associations.** Organisations that connect industry players, research institutions, and policymakers to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaborative initiatives.
- **Policy agents.** Local, national and European governmental institutions and regulatory bodies responsible for environmental policies, industrial waste governance and sustainability frameworks.

- **Civil society.** Local associations, trade unions, educational sector, and communities engaging with environment risk impacts, waste management and local policies.
- **Academia & RTOs.** Universities, research centres and technical experts conducting studies related to environmental science, risk assessment and sustainable waste management.
- **NGOs.** Non-governmental organisations, environmental advocacy groups and local community representatives concerned with social and environmental impacts.

The stakeholder database is a dynamic resource, updated as new actors, partnerships, and emerging issues are identified. To ensure effective stakeholder engagement, the FIC-Fighters project employs structured communication tools, including stakeholder matrices (categorising stakeholders based on *Power* or *Influence* and *Interest* or engagement priority strategies) (see *deliverable D6.1*).

2. Methodology

The methodology outlined in this deliverable presents the systematic approach adopted to identify and map stakeholders relevant to the phosphogypsum (PG) valorisation process and its environmental, social, and governance (ESG) dimensions. The identification of stakeholders extends beyond mere categorisation; it involves a comprehensive analysis of relationships, power and engagement potential within the broader framework of sustainable PG management.

Our approach incorporates a database that organises a diverse range of information, including stakeholder categories, roles, levels of power and interest, and their interconnections in the context of PG valorisation. Given the evolving nature of stakeholder interests and project developments, this methodology ensures flexibility to accommodate updates and refinements throughout the project's lifespan.

A thorough and inclusive process has been prioritised, encompassing the identification of key and secondary data sources, systematic data collection, and organisation of stakeholder information. This structured approach ensures that the stakeholder database functions not only as a repository of information but as a strategic tool for engagement, decision-making, and dissemination of project insights. It facilitates effective communication with policymakers, industry actors, researchers, civil society, and local communities, ensuring that stakeholder interactions align with the project's social impact assessment and governance objectives.

This methodology aims to establish a robust foundation for stakeholder engagement and communication strategies, ensuring that project activities are informed by a nuanced understanding of the diverse actors involved in the environmental and social governance of PG stacks. This section sets the stage for a detailed exposition of the methods employed in the stakeholder mapping process, contributing to a structured and impactful engagement strategy.

2.1. Construction of database structure

The initial step in the stakeholder mapping process has been the creation of a comprehensive database to collect and organise relevant information. This database includes multiple fields such as stakeholder category, subcategory, stakeholder name, stakeholder description, geographical scope, power, , interest, challenges, contact details, and relevant references (URLs). This structured format ensures efficient categorisation, accessibility, and continuous updating as new stakeholders are identified or additional information becomes available.

2.1.1. Identification of main stakeholder categories

In the context of phosphogypsum valorisation understanding the diverse range of stakeholders is essential. This report has integrated insights from relevant EU projects while tailoring the categorisation to the specific challenges and opportunities of PG management and reuse.

The final stakeholder categories identified are:

- **Industry and business.** This category includes entities involved in the processing, transformation, and potential reuse of PG. It encompasses industrial end-users, waste management companies, technology developers, and businesses exploring PG-based applications. These organisations play a critical role in market uptake, environmental compliance, and advancing responsible practices and circular solutions.
- **Clusters & associations.** Groups of interconnected companies, specialised suppliers, service providers, and institutions collaborating to enhance competitiveness, innovation, and knowledge-sharing related to PG valorisation. These networks facilitate industrial synergies and regulatory adaptation.
- **Policy agents and public administration.** Governmental and regulatory bodies responsible for developing, overseeing, and enforcing policies and regulations related to industrial by-products and environmental governance. This category includes local, national, and EU-level institutions that influence PG management strategies, permitting, and sustainability frameworks.
- **Civil society.** This group includes community-based organisations, labour unions, and affected local communities. Their role is crucial in public acceptance and ensuring responsible industrial practices related to PG management.
- **Academia and research and technology organisations (RTOs).** Universities, research institutes, and technology centres focused on environmental sciences, material characterisation, and sustainable solutions for PG reuse. These stakeholders contribute to scientific validation, policy recommendations, and process innovation.
- **Non-governmental organisations (NGOs).** Organisations addressing environmental, health, and socio-economic concerns related to PG management. NGOs are key in advocating for transparency, corporate responsibility, and community engagement in projects involving industrial by-products.
- **Media.** Entities responsible for disseminating information and shaping public discourse on PG-related topics, including environmental sustainability, industrial waste policies, and governance. Journalists, digital platforms, and specialised publications play a key role in public awareness and policy influence.

These broad categories include various subcategories that reflect the different roles and functions stakeholders hold within the project ecosystem. The detailed subcategories are presented in

Table 1 and **Figure 1**.

By structuring the stakeholder mapping in this way, FIC-Fighters ensures that all relevant actors are identified, their interests understood, and their potential roles in the sustainable management of PG effectively integrated into the project.

Table 1. Stakeholder sub-categories structure

id	category 1	id2	Subcategory
1	Industry and business	1.1.	Phosphoric acid manufacturers and suppliers (PG generators)
		1.2.	Pretreatment and conditioning of PG
		1.3.	Processing and valorisation of PG
		1.4.	Technology provider/research
		1.5.	Contractor /supplier / services
		1.6.	Investor
		1.7.	Land developers
		1.8.	Exploration and development
		1.9.	End users' companies (battery manufacturers, detergent, paper, fertiliser and cement companies)
2	Clusters & Associations	2.1.	Industrial groups
		2.2.	Technology platform
		2.4.	Public-private Partnership
		2.5.	State-dependant System
3	Policy agents	3.1.	Government Departments/Ministries
		3.2.	Regulatory Bodies
		3.3.	Local Government
		3.4.	Regional Government
		3.5.	Legislative Bodies
		3.6.	International Policy Organisations
		3.7.	Public Advisory Organisations
4	Civil society	4.1.	Local association/organisation
		4.2.	Trade union
		4.3.	Educational sector
5	Academia & RTOs	5.1.	University
		5.2.	Research centres
		5.3.	Innovation hubs
6	NGOS	6.1.	Environmental Protection organisations
		6.2.	Climate Change and Energy
		6.3.	Environmental Education and Awareness

id	category 1	id2	Subcategory
		6.4.	Sustainable Development
		6.5.	Environmental Justice
		6.6	Policy and Advocacy
		6.7	Water and Marine Conservation
7	Media	7.1.	National Media
		7.2.	Regional Media
		7.3.	Local Media

Figure 1. Graphical distribution of subcategories in categories of stakeholders (source: own elaboration)

2.1.2. Fields of information on the database

The stakeholder database is designed to provide a structured and comprehensive understanding of the diverse actors involved in phosphogypsum valorisation and environmental governance. The database facilitates the categorisation, analysis and engagement of stakeholders based on their roles, power, interests, and challenges.

This section outlines the specific fields of information included in the database, ensuring that each entry contributes to the project's strategic objectives. The collected data ranges from basic identification details to more detailed insights into stakeholder influence, engagement levels, and communication preferences. The methodology ensures that all recorded information serves a clear purpose in improving stakeholder interaction and supporting the successful development of the project.

The database is structured into the following fields:

- **Partner:** Identification of the project partner responsible for completing the stakeholder entry (acronym).
- **Full name:** Name of the person entering the stakeholder data.
- **Stk name:** Official name of the stakeholder.
- **Stk category:** Classification of the stakeholder into one of the predefined categories: industry, clusters and associations, policy agents, civil society, academia and RTOs, NGOs, or media.
- **Stk subcategory:** Classification of the stakeholder into one of the predefined subcategories per main categories.
- **Stk representative:** Name of the primary contact person within the stakeholder organisation.
- **Engagement strategy:** Classification of stakeholders according to their positioning in the Power–Interest matrix, used to define the appropriate level and type of engagement in relation to the FIC-Fighters project and its outcomes:
 1. Engage closely and influence actively (high power, high interest)
 2. Keep satisfied (high power, low interest)
 3. Keep informed (low power, high interest)
 4. Monitor (low power, low interest)
- **Contact:** Contact details such as email and phone number.
- **Location:** Geographical location of the stakeholder's operations.
- **EU countries:** Specification of whether the stakeholder operates within the European Union, listed according to the "EU countries" sheet.
- **Scope area:** The geographical scope of stakeholder power, categorised as international (non-UE), European level, national, regional, or linked to a specific case study.
- **STKH description:** Short description of the stakeholder, including its main activities, relevance to PG valorisation, and key contributions.
- **Power:** Indicates the stakeholder's capability to influence the project, shaping policies, regulations, industry practices or public perception regarding the project. It is categorised as high or low.
- **Interest:** Refers to the degree of relevance of the project to the stakeholder, indicated by their level of engagement or involvement with the project and related issues, and categorised as high or low.
- **Comments:** Open field for additional remarks or observations.

- **Challenges:** Any known obstacles or issues related to stakeholder engagement, such as communication barriers, scheduling conflicts, or diverging interests.
- **Urls:** Webpage or other contact information, if available.

This structured approach allows the project to effectively track and engage with stakeholders, ensuring that all relevant actors are mapped, their roles understood, and their potential contributions leveraged. The stakeholder database will be continuously updated to reflect changes in engagement levels, project needs and stakeholder priorities.

2.2. Data gathering and systematization

The data gathering and systematisation phase focuses on the meticulous collection and organisation of relevant information related to the governance, environmental and social aspects of Phosphogypsum (PG) stacks. This phase involves a strategic approach to identifying viable data sources, mapping key stakeholders at local, national and European levels, and compiling essential details that will contribute to the development of a comprehensive and evolving stakeholder database. Emphasising thoroughness and precision, this process ensures that the information collected is both extensive and conducive to in-depth analysis.

2.2.1. Identification of sources of information

The process began with a systematic identification of relevant data sources, combining secondary research with primary stakeholder input from project partners. This approach ensured a comprehensive and context-specific mapping of stakeholders related to the governance, environmental management, and social impact of Phosphogypsum (PG) stacks.

To achieve this, the project team conducted **direct consultations** with case study partners to jointly identify key stakeholders at regional, national and European levels. These discussions provided first-hand insights into local regulatory bodies, research institutions, industry representatives, and civil society organisations involved in PG stack management. As part of this collaborative effort, partners contributed directly to an interactive stakeholder database, structured as an evolving Excel-based repository.

In addition to primary stakeholder input, an extensive review of **secondary information** sources has been conducted to complement and validate the mapping process. To enhance this process, Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, specifically Named Entity Recognition (NER), support the automated extraction of key stakeholders from policy documents, research reports, and media sources. Applied to Deliverable D5.1 Base Report on the Social Perception of Phosphogypsum Stacks, this method identifies government agencies, industry actors, research institutions, and civil society organisations. The extracted entities are cross-referenced with existing stakeholder data to validate their relevance and influence, improving coverage and efficiency.

Furthermore, the following key platforms and institutions provided valuable information on relevant policies, environmental regulations, research initiatives, and stakeholder networks:

- European Environment Agency (EEA). Provides data on environmental policies, impact assessments, and regulatory frameworks relevant to PG stack management.
<https://www.eea.europa.eu>

- Joint Research Centre (JRC). The European Commission's science and knowledge service, offering scientific evidence and policy support for environmental governance. https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/index_en
- CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service). The European Commission's primary database of research project results, including studies on environmental sustainability and industrial waste. <https://cordis.europa.eu/>
- Eurostat. Offers statistical data on environmental and industrial sectors within the EU, helping to contextualise stakeholder engagement strategies. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>
- European NORM Association (ENA). Network dedicated to addressing issues related to Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM) in industries. It promotes knowledge exchange, regulatory development, and best practices for the safe management of NORM across Europe.
- European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform (ESPP). ESPP brings together companies, scientists and stakeholders for sustainable phosphorus management and nutrient recycling. <https://www.phosphorusplatform.eu/>
- European Federation of Waste Management and Environmental Services (FEAD). Represents the waste management sector and its role in environmental policies. <https://fead.be/>
- EJAtlas - Global Atlas of Environmental Justice. Maps environmental conflicts, highlighting community concerns related to industrial and environmental projects. <https://ejatlas.org/>
- International Solid Waste Association (ISWA). Provides insights into waste management strategies relevant to PG stacks and industrial waste governance. <https://www.iswa.org/>
- Bureau of International Recycling (BIR). Covers industry practices related to waste recovery and recycling. <https://bir.org/>
- SHARE platform. Platform for Social Sciences and humanities research on ionising radiation, including members who have conducted research on NORM in society.
- Google. Used for targeted searches to identify additional stakeholders, reports, and case studies.

These secondary sources enabled the team to:

- Identify major EU projects linked to the environmental and social impact of industrial waste, providing insights into key stakeholders and governance structures.
- Locate reports and databases containing information on regulatory frameworks, environmental assessments, and relevant stakeholder engagement initiatives.
- Complement primary data collection by cross-referencing stakeholders, organisations, and case studies identified through project partner consultations.

To maintain an up-to-date and dynamic stakeholder database, the project has adopted an iterative approach, allowing for the continuous inclusion of new stakeholders and updates throughout its duration. By maintaining an open channel for contributions from case study partners, the database remains a living resource, adaptable to project progress and emerging developments. This ensures that stakeholder engagement remains relevant, comprehensive and aligned with evolving policy and social considerations related to PG stacks.

2.2.2. Data importation into the database

After systematization, the data have been imported into our database. This step involves the transfer of data from our systematized records into the database structure. Special attention has been paid to the data format and integrity during this step to prevent any errors or data loss.

2.2.3. Review of the database

Finally, the database has been reviewed and refined. This step involves checking for accuracy, filling in any gaps in the data, and ensuring that the information is up-to-date and relevant. The database will be updated periodically until the end of the project.

2.3. Stakeholder cards methodology

To complement the identification work of stakeholders, a **stakeholder card** has been designed for each stakeholder profile. This stakeholder card will aid in achieving a deeper understanding of each profile, thereby assisting in the development of future engagement and communication strategies with stakeholders.

The primary objectives of the stakeholder profile cards are to:

- Provide a clear and concise summary of each stakeholder's interests, power, and expectations.
- Serve as a reference tool for engaging with and addressing the concerns of each stakeholder group.

The stakeholder cards offer a comprehensive snapshot of stakeholder dynamics and enhance the precision of our engagement efforts. In sum, the stakeholder profile cards are not just informational tools; they are strategic assets that enable us to navigate the complexities of stakeholder relationships within this sector.

2.3.1. Profile card structure

Each field of the stakeholder card has been carefully defined to capture the most critical and relevant aspects of stakeholder profiles, ensuring that the data is strategically aligned to inform and shape future engagement and communication strategies effectively. Each stakeholder profile card comprises the following fields:

- **Identification and contact:** Names, affiliations, and contact information of primary representatives from industry, policy, research, NGOs, civil society, and media.
- **Objectives:** Key goals, initiatives, and areas of focus related to PG management, valorisation, environmental sustainability, and regulatory compliance.
- **Power and Interest:** The capacity of stakeholders to influence PG-related policies, industrial practices, public perception, and governance frameworks; and the value that stakeholders attribute to the project and its outcomes.
- **Needs and expectations:** Requirements for cooperation, anticipated project outcomes, and stakeholder priorities regarding safe and sustainable PG management.

- **Resources and capabilities:** Available tools, expertise, technological solutions, research capacities, and industrial assets that enable the stakeholder to contribute to or shape PG valorisation and remediation efforts.
- **History of relationships:** Past interactions with PG valorisation projects, environmental governance frameworks, policy institutions, research initiatives, and affected communities.
- **Communication and engagement:** Preferred methods and channels for interaction, historical engagement with PG-related initiatives, and best practices for effective collaboration.
- **Perspective and vision:** Long-term outlook on PG valorisation, circular economy strategies, and sustainable waste management practices.
- **Legal and regulatory aspects:** Compliance obligations, regulatory impacts, and involvement in PG-related environmental policies, industrial standards, and safety regulations.
- **Risks and challenges:** Potential obstacles and concerns, including technical limitations, regulatory uncertainties, environmental risks, economic feasibility, and societal acceptance of PG valorisation.

2.3.2. Stakeholder strategy

Stakeholders are categorised based on their level of Power—their capability to influence decisions, policies, and practices related to PG stacks management, perception, and recycling—and their level of Interest, which reflects their potential involvement in the project.

According to this Power–Interest matrix, four main quadrants can be identified (see *Deliverable 6.1*), each associated with a specific engagement and stakeholder management strategy:

- High power, high interest: *engage closely* and influence actively, high effort, regular detailed communication and dialogue, taking their view into account.
- High power, low interest: *keep satisfied*, moderate effort, periodical information, keeping their view into account.
- Low power, high interest: *keep informed*, moderate effort, periodical information and feedback.
- Low power, low interest: *monitor*, least effort, periodical re-evaluation.

Each stakeholder identified through the mapping exercise has been classified within one quadrant, which aims to help engagement strategy prioritisation based on their decision-making authority (power) and their level of interest in relation to the FIC-Fighters project and outcomes.

3. Results : Stakeholder cards

3.1. Industry and business

Industry and business	
Description	Businesses and corporations involved in phosphoric acid production—generating phosphogypsum (PG) as a by-product—and associated services or technologies for PG stack

Industry and business	
	management, processing, transformation, and potential reuse of PG. It encompasses industrial end-users, waste management companies, technology developers, and businesses exploring PG-based applications. These organisations play a critical role in market uptake, environmental compliance, and advancing responsible practices and circular solutions. They are primarily profit-driven and play a critical role in ensuring responsible handling, reuse, or disposal of PG, while also contributing to regional economic growth, employment, and technological advancement.
Identification and contact	Companies involved in phosphate processing, chemical production, fertilisers, construction materials, and industrial waste management. Many have sustainability or environmental compliance departments.
Objectives	Focus on phosphogypsum (PG) valorisation, secondary raw material recovery, and CO ₂ emissions reduction. Goals include developing circular economy models, optimising waste-to-resource strategies, and reducing landfill dependency. Compliance with EU environmental policies and industrial by-product reuse regulations is a priority.
Power and Interest	Industry and business stakeholders hold substantial power through their roles in phosphogypsum generation, processing, or their potential as end-users, as well as their participation in regulatory and market contexts. Their interest is considered high, driven by cost efficiency and innovation opportunities (mainly in the case of producers and end-users companies), leading to Engage closely or Keep satisfied engagement strategies, depending on the specific cases.
Needs and expectations	Require technical validation and regulatory frameworks to support PG reuse in industry. Seek economic incentives for sustainable waste recovery, R&D collaboration for material processing innovations, and pilot-scale demonstrations to assess feasibility. Concerns about cost-efficiency and market acceptance of secondary materials.
Resources and capabilities	Significant financial, human, and technological capacity for R&D in waste valorisation, material recovery, and industrial by-product reuse. Experience in industrial-scale chemical processes, cement formulation, and fertiliser production. Participate in EU-funded sustainability projects and environmental management systems.
History of relationships	Collaborate with research institutions, regulatory bodies, and NGOs in sustainability projects. Active in corporate sustainability reporting and pilot projects related to circular economy and industrial symbiosis.
Communication and engagement	Engage in EU policy consultations, industry conferences, and technical working groups. Prefer formal reports, regulatory updates, and industry-led initiatives. Participate in digital platforms such as the PG Virtual Forum.
Perspective and vision	Long-term focus on decarbonisation, circular resource use, and regulatory compliance. Integrating safe and sustainable-by-design (SSbD) principles into industrial production and waste management.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Must comply with EU and global regulations on waste recovery, emissions, hazardous material management, and fertiliser safety standards. Monitoring changes in Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), waste classification frameworks, and funding opportunities.
Risks and challenges	Challenges in scaling up PG-based materials for construction and industry. Regulatory uncertainties on waste classification and material reuse. Need for market acceptance, standardisation of secondary raw materials, and adaptation of existing processes.

3.2. Clusters & Associations

Clusters & Associations	
Description	Groups of interconnected organisations, specialized suppliers, service providers, and associated institutions in the phosphogypsum (PG) domain that collaborate to address common challenges, share expertise, and drive innovation in PG stack management.
Identification and contact	Industry clusters, trade associations, and sectoral alliances related to phosphate processing, fertilisers, cement, rare earth elements (REEs), chemicals, and industrial waste management. Key contacts include policy officers, technical coordinators, and sustainability representatives.
Objectives	Focus on circular economy policies, industrial symbiosis, waste valorisation, and regulatory compliance. Support members in adopting sustainable practices, developing secondary raw material markets, and securing EU funding for innovation projects.
Power and Interest	Clusters and associations mainly act as coordination, advocacy, and knowledge-sharing bodies linking industry, research, and policy. Their power and interest vary considerably, with most positioned under Keep informed or Monitor, while a smaller group of EU-level and PG- or NORM-focused associations show higher relevance and are engaged through Keep satisfied or Engage closely strategies
Needs and expectations	Require scientific evidence, regulatory updates, and policy recommendations to advocate for phosphogypsum (PG) reuse, circular solutions, and industrial waste valorisation. Seek collaborative research, public-private partnerships, and technology transfer opportunities.
Resources and capabilities	Act as knowledge hubs connecting industry, academia, and policymakers. Provide technical expertise, networking platforms, and policy advocacy. Organise workshops, industry reports, and best practice exchanges.
History of relationships	Work with EU institutions, national governments, and international sustainability networks. Participate in Horizon Europe projects, circular economy initiatives, and industrial symbiosis programmes.
Communication and engagement	Engage through policy briefings, technical committees, and industry events. Use white papers, regulatory position statements, and stakeholder consultations to power decision-making. Contribute to EU-funded platforms and virtual forums.
Perspective and vision	Support harmonised regulatory frameworks, cross-sectoral collaboration, and circular economy adoption. Advocate for economic incentives and policy support for industrial waste recovery and sustainable material cycles.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Monitor and shape EU directives on waste classification, secondary raw materials, emissions, and industrial waste recovery. Provide guidance on compliance with Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), REACH, and circular economy targets.
Risks and challenges	Barriers in regulatory harmonisation, market acceptance of secondary raw materials, and industry adaptation to new sustainability requirements. Need for policy alignment, funding mechanisms, and standardisation of circular economy practices.

3.3. Policy Agents

Policy Agents and Public Administration	
Description	Governmental and non-governmental entities that develop, implement, and oversee policies, regulations, and standards for phosphogypsum (PG) stack management, aiming to ensure compliance, minimize environmental impact, and protect public health.
Identification and contact	Government agencies, regulatory bodies, and EU institutions responsible for environmental policy, waste management, industrial sustainability, and circular economy regulations. Key contacts include policy advisors, environmental regulators, and circular economy coordinators.
Objectives	Focus on policy implementation, regulatory enforcement, and sustainability targets. Support waste valorisation, industrial decarbonisation, and secondary raw material markets. Align policies with EU Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan, and Waste Framework Directive.
Power and Interest	Policy agents are mainly responsible for setting and enforcing regulatory frameworks, therefore, they play a decisive role in phosphogypsum management. Their authority to define legislation, approve permits, allocate funding, and oversee compliance, combined with strong interest linked to environmental and public health mandates, places most of them within the Engage closely and influence actively engagement strategy.
Needs and expectations	Require scientific data, industry feedback, and impact assessments to design effective waste valorisation policies. Seek stakeholder engagement, feasibility studies, and cross-sector collaboration to ensure policy alignment with industrial innovation and environmental goals.
Resources and capabilities	Provide legislative tools, regulatory oversight, and public funding mechanisms. Facilitate research grants, pilot projects, and policy incentives for circular economy initiatives. Monitor compliance with environmental regulations and industrial waste management directives.
History of relationships	Collaborate with research institutions, industry associations, and EU-funded sustainability projects. Engage in policy dialogues, intergovernmental forums, and standardisation initiatives related to waste recovery and industrial sustainability.
Communication and engagement	Use public consultations, regulatory reports, and legislative updates to inform stakeholders. Participate in industry forums, technical committees, and cross-sector workshops. Engage through public-private partnerships and funding programmes.
Perspective and vision	Support harmonised waste management frameworks, investment in circular technologies, and long-term sustainability policies. Promote legislative clarity, innovation-driven policy support, and sector-wide adaptation to EU environmental goals.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Oversee waste classification laws, secondary raw material regulations, emissions standards, and industrial waste recovery policies. Align national frameworks with EU sustainability directives and circular economy targets.
Risks and challenges	Barriers in policy harmonisation, enforcement capacity, and industry adaptation. Challenges in scaling waste recovery systems, ensuring compliance, and securing public-private investment for circular economy transitions.

3.4. Civil Society

Civil Society	
Description	Community-based groups, educational sector, local NGOs, labour unions, and organisations that represent and advocate for the interests, well-being, and rights of people potentially affected by phosphogypsum stacks, seeking transparency, accountability, and fair treatment in PG management processes.
Identification and contact	Includes community groups, trade unions, grassroots organisations, and local NGOs and media representatives. Key contacts include community leaders, educational, environmental and health sectors, and union representatives.
Objectives	Focus on social and environmental impacts of industrial activities, waste management, and public health. Advocate for responsible industrial practices, workers' rights, environmental protection, and transparency. Seek public engagement in decision-making and sustainable economic transitions.
Power and Interest	Civil society stakeholders generally show high concern regarding environmental and health impacts but have limited formal decision-making capacity. Mostly it is positioned under Keep informed communication strategy. However, in the framework of FICFighters it has been decided as a principle of action and good practice to address Engage closely strategies in relation to local communities at the study cases of the project.
Needs and expectations	Demand transparency, accountability, and meaningful participation in industrial projects and regulatory processes. Seek access to information, community consultations, and inclusion in policy discussions. Expect companies and authorities to address environmental and social concerns.
Resources and capabilities	Leverage community networks, social mobilisation, media outreach, and advocacy platforms. Possess expertise in environmental law, labour rights, public health, and community organising. Utilise social media, investigative journalism, and grassroots activism to power decisions.
History of relationships	Engage with government agencies, industry, and NGOs on sustainability initiatives, labour rights, and environmental justice. Past interactions range from cooperative collaborations to confrontational advocacy, depending on corporate and government approaches to social and environmental responsibility.
Communication and engagement	Use public forums, social media, press releases, petitions, and direct action to raise awareness. Participate in community consultations and workshops, citizen science projects, and public campaigns to promote sustainable development and responsible industrial practices.
Perspective and vision	Advocate for sustainability, social justice, and community well-being. Support a just transition that considers environmental protection, workers' rights, and equitable economic development. Push for long-term environmental stewardship and public health safeguards.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Monitor compliance with environmental and social regulations. Advocate for stricter industrial waste management policies, pollution control measures, and human rights protections. Engage in legal challenges and policy reforms to strengthen corporate and government accountability.
Risks and challenges	Barriers in accessing decision-making processes, obtaining reliable environmental data, and securing long-term funding. Face marginalisation, opposition from industry, and limited regulatory enforcement. Risk of social conflicts due to industrial developments impacting local communities.

3.5. Academia & RTOs

Academia & RTOs	
Description	Educational, research, and technological institutions dedicated to advancing knowledge, innovation, and best practices in phosphogypsum stack management, encompassing scientific studies, technological development, and capacity-building to ensure environmental and public health safeguards.
Identification and contact	Universities, research centres, and technology institutes working on industrial waste valorisation, circular economy, environmental engineering, materials science, and chemical process optimisation. Key contacts include researchers, laboratory directors, and technology transfer officers.
Objectives	Focus on developing scientific knowledge, technological innovations, and sustainable industrial practices. Support waste-to-resource strategies, secondary raw material recovery, and process efficiency improvements. Align research with EU Green Deal, Horizon Europe, and circular economy policies.
Power and Interest	Academia and RTOs contribute primarily through knowledge generation, scientific evidence, and technical expertise relevant to PG management, rather than through formal decision-making authority. Interest is generally high due to research relevance and access to data, while power is typically limited; therefore, most stakeholders are positioned under Keep informed or Monitor, with a small number of key research actors Engaged closely.
Needs and expectations	Require funding, industry partnerships, and regulatory alignment to develop and scale innovative waste recovery solutions. Seek access to industrial data, demonstration sites, and collaborative projects to validate new materials, processes, and recycling technologies.
Resources and capabilities	Possess analytical laboratories, pilot-scale facilities, and computational modelling tools for material characterisation, process optimisation, and environmental impact assessments. Provide scientific publications, technical reports, and policy insights.
History of relationships	Collaborate with industry, policymakers, industrial consortia, and innovation networks. Participate in regulatory discussions, technology transfer initiatives, and public-private partnerships.
Communication and engagement	Use scientific conferences, peer-reviewed publications, and policy briefs to disseminate research. Engage in technical workshops, industry panels, and open-access data platforms. Contribute to EU research networks and standardisation bodies.
Perspective and vision	Support science-based policymaking, cross-sector innovation, and knowledge-driven sustainability transitions. Promote circular economy education, digitalisation in resource management, and interdisciplinary collaboration.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Align research activities with EU environmental regulations, waste classification frameworks, and industrial emissions standards. Address intellectual property management, ethical research compliance, and technology deployment pathways.
Risks and challenges	Barriers in scaling laboratory research to industrial applications, securing long-term funding, and aligning academic research with industry needs. Challenges in standardisation, regulatory approval, and technology commercialisation.

3.6. NGOs

NGOs	
Description	Organisations working on environmental, social, and policy issues related to phosphogypsum stack management, advocating for responsible practices and community engagement.
Identification and contact	Environmental, social, and sustainability-focused non-governmental organisations (NGOs) working on waste management, circular economy, pollution reduction, industrial sustainability, environmental justice, and public health impacts of PG stacks. Key contacts include programme managers, policy coordinators, and advocacy specialists.
Objectives	Focus on environmental protection, social responsibility, public health, and policy advocacy. Support circular economy adoption, industrial waste reduction, pollution prevention, and community engagement. Align activities with EU Green Deal, zero waste policies, extended producer responsibility (EPR) frameworks, and health impact assessments.
Power and Interest	NGOs generally show high interest in the project due to their focus on environmental protection, public health, and social accountability related to PG stacks, while their formal decision-making power is usually limited. Most are therefore positioned under Keep informed or Monitor, with a smaller group of highly visible or influential environmental NGOs may require Engage closely strategies due to their capacity to shape public debate and policy attention. In the case of FICFighters, similarly as in the case of Civil Society, the local NGOs have been also included in this last strategy, actively involving them.
Needs and expectations	Require scientific data, policy insights, and industry cooperation to develop evidence-based advocacy and community-driven initiatives. Seek partnerships with research institutions, government agencies, and industry players to support waste valorisation, pollution monitoring, and sustainability education.
Resources and capabilities	Provide policy analysis, environmental monitoring, and stakeholder mobilisation. Possess expertise in community engagement, life cycle assessments, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) evaluation. Organise campaigns, reports, and training programmes on circular economy, pollution reduction, and public health impacts.
History of relationships	Collaborate with government agencies, academia, industry associations, and civil society groups on sustainability projects, public health studies, pollution monitoring, and regulatory advocacy. Participate in EU policy consultations, multi-stakeholder initiatives, and environmental monitoring programmes.
Communication and engagement	Engage through public reports, health impact assessments, policy briefings, media campaigns, and stakeholder workshops. Use social media, petitions, and open forums to power decision-making. Participate in EU-funded networks, advisory committees, and sustainability summits.
Perspective and vision	Promote stronger environmental and public health regulations, corporate accountability, and inclusive stakeholder engagement. Advocate for circular economy integration, pollution prevention, and just transition policies. Support community-driven solutions, environmental justice, and participatory governance models.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Monitor compliance with EU environmental policies, waste management regulations, industrial emissions standards, and public health directives. Contribute to policy reviews, impact assessments, watchdog reports, and legal actions for regulatory improvements.
Risks and challenges	Barriers in securing long-term funding, maintaining power in policy discussions, and ensuring alignment with industrial innovation. Challenges in data access, industry

NGOs	
	cooperation, bridging regulatory gaps, and addressing health risks associated with PG stacks.

3.7. Media

Media	
Description	Entities disseminating information and shaping public opinion regarding phosphogypsum stack management or related topics.
Identification and contact	Includes news outlets, journalism organisations, industry publications, digital media platforms, and independent content creators covering environmental issues, industrial waste management, circular economy, and sustainability. Key contacts include journalists, editors, and producers with expertise in investigative reporting, policy analysis, and industry developments.
Objectives	Focus on reporting industry practices, environmental impacts, regulatory changes, and public concerns. Aim to inform, investigate, and shape public opinion by covering phosphogypsum management, circular economy policies, and industrial sustainability trends.
Power and Interest	The widest coverage media generally show low to moderate interest in the PG stacks and research projects, reflected in limited and episodic coverage of PG-related issues, and therefore have a relatively low role in shaping public attention at this stage. The exception is the local media where PG stacks are located. Therefore, most media stakeholders are positioned under Keep informed or monitored, while a small number of local media with demonstrated, sustained coverage are prioritised for Engage closely to support accurate and contextualised dissemination of the project.
Needs and expectations	Require access to accurate, transparent, and timely information from government agencies, industry representatives, and research institutions. Expect expert commentary, data insights, and press availability for balanced reporting on waste valorisation, pollution control, and circular economy transitions.
Resources and capabilities	Possess investigative journalism tools, data analysis platforms, and mass communication channels. Leverage digital and traditional media to reach broad audiences. Use fact-checking, interviews, and multimedia content to report industry developments.
History of relationships	Engage with government agencies, industry, NGOs, and academia to report on policy decisions, environmental impact studies, and industrial practices. Relations can be collaborative or adversarial, depending on transparency and access to information.
Communication and engagement	Use news articles, reports, documentaries, podcasts, and digital platforms to communicate findings. Engage through interviews, public forums, investigative features, and social media interactions. Participate in press briefings, industry events, and policy discussions.
Perspective and vision	Support independent, evidence-based journalism on industrial sustainability, waste management, and environmental policies. Promote public access to information, corporate accountability, and informed decision-making. Seek balanced, data-driven narratives on industrial transitions.
Legal and regulatory aspects	Operate within press freedom laws, ethical journalism standards, and media regulations. Navigate libel, slander, and access to information laws when covering corporate and policy developments. Monitor EU media transparency policies and public disclosure requirements.

Media

Risks and challenges

Face challenges in accessing reliable data, industry transparency, and corporate responses to investigations. Risk legal pressures, misinformation, and power from political or corporate interests. Struggle with balancing editorial independence and funding constraints.

4. Results: Stakeholder database

4.1. Distribution by categories

The stakeholder database is systematically undergoing an updating process, ensuring continuous expansion and refinement. Currently, it comprises **258 stakeholders** across all case studies and at the general level, including those stakeholders with a broader perspective at the international and EU levels.

As mentioned before, the database resulting from this stakeholder mapping exercise is a tool that will be continuously enriched throughout the life of the project. It is a dynamic working instrument in constant evolution and improvement, so the data presented in this chapter reflect a ‘snapshot’ of the current moment.

The current distribution across stakeholder profiles is as follows:

- Industry and business: 41 stakeholders
- Clusters & Associations: 33 stakeholders
- Policy agents: 60 stakeholders
- Civil society: 22 stakeholders
- Academia & RTOs: 38 stakeholders
- NGOs: 28 stakeholders
- Media: 36 stakeholders

The distribution of stakeholders across categories and case studies in the FIC-FIGHTERS project is as follows:

- **Policy Agents** (60) are present across all case studies, with the highest numbers in Veles (18), Kutina (10), Barreiro (7), Turnu Magurele (6), Prahovo (5), and Cartagena (4).
- **Academia & RTOs** (38) are distributed among general stakeholders (8), Kutina (6), Veles (6), Barreiro (5), Prahovo (5), Turnu Magurele (4), and Cartagena (4).
- **Industry and Business** (41) are primarily located in Veles (11), Kutina (10), Barreiro (4), Prahovo (4), Cartagena (3), and Turnu Magurele (2), with 7 listed under general stakeholders.
- **Clusters & Associations** (33) have the largest presence in general stakeholders (21), with additional representation in Veles (5), Barreiro (5), Prahovo (1), and Kutina (1).
- **NGOs** (28) appear in Veles (6), Kutina (7), Barreiro (3), Prahovo (3), Cartagena (2), Turnu Magurele (1), and general stakeholders (6).
- **Civil Society** (22) is represented in Veles (2), Barreiro (3), Kutina (3), Prahovo (4), Turnu Magurele (2), Cartagena (3), and general stakeholders (5).
- **Media** (36) is distributed among Cartagena (7), Veles (6), Barreiro (3), Kutina (6), Prahovo (6), Turnu Magurele (4), and general stakeholders (4).

Table 2. Distribution of stakeholders in the study case and European level

Category	Case Study level	European level
Industry and Business	34	7
Clusters & Associations	12	21
Policy Agents	50	10
Civil Society	17	5
Academia & RTOs	30	8
NGOs	22	6
Media	32	4
Total	197	61

Figure 2. Map of distribution of stakeholders by Case Study (source: own elaboration)

Figure 3. Distribution of stakeholders by category in the database (case study and non-case study)
(Source: own elaboration)

5. Conclusions

The objective of deliverable D5.2 is to identify and categorize the key actors involved in or affected by phosphogypsum (PG) management and valorisation at different levels as local, national, and European. The ongoing process aims to provide a structured approach to stakeholder engagement, ensuring that relevant perspectives are documented and available for further project activities.

Stakeholder mapping was conducted through a systematic approach that classified stakeholders based on their Power and Interest. The methodology included the collection and organization of stakeholder data into a structured database, allowing for a clear overview of their distribution across six case study regions and at the European level. This process involved gathering information from various sources, including project partners, institutional databases, and public records, ensuring a broad and representative identification of stakeholders.

The result of this process is a database comprising **258 stakeholders**, categorized into policy agents, industry, academia and research organizations, NGOs, civil society, media, and clusters & associations. The database is designed to be a dynamic tool, allowing updates throughout the project as new stakeholders emerge or engagement evolves.

The results of the stakeholder mapping show that policy agents (60) represent the largest stakeholder group across all case studies. Academia & RTOs (38) and industry and business (41) are also widely represented, particularly in Veles, Kutina, and Barreiro. Clusters & associations (33) and NGOs (28) are present across multiple case studies, while civil society (22) and media (36) have a more varied distribution.

This mapping aligns with the project's approach to connecting technical expertise with societal perspectives and ensuring early and inclusive participation from relevant stakeholders. The collected data will support upcoming tasks, including assessing the social impact of PG stacks, promoting stakeholder involvement in decision-making, and developing regulatory recommendations. By structuring stakeholder engagement in a dynamic and adaptable way, this deliverable contributes to the overall efforts of the FIC-Fighters project to address PG-related challenges through informed and collaborative strategies.